

STUDY OF MARKETING TECHNIQUES OF ORGANIC AND INORGANIC MOBILE APPLICATIONS IN ANDROID OPERATING SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

With the advent of digital era, Smartphones usage witnessed tremendous growth in mobile applications development field. This made a platform for Start-ups as well as for Established organizations who are developing applications to deliver and meet requirements of different clients and customers. Android Mobile Applications became stepping stone of this era and its cross-platform features led to various applications making way to PlayStore. This paper focuses on the study of customer preferences and its related factors regarding Android Mobile Applications which is both exploratory and descriptive. Anova, a statistical tool was used to test the hypothesis. The result of this study made evident that Usability, Unique and Appealing Design are few important factors contributing to an application usage.

Key words: Android Mobile Applications, Customer Preferences, Anova tool, Chi Square Test

Cite this Article: Dr. Hemanth Kumar. S and Dittakavi Ramya Sri, Study of Marketing Techniques of Organic and Inorganic Mobile Applications In Android Operating System. *International Journal of Management*, 7(7), 2016, pp. 352–362.

<http://www.iaeme.com/IJM/issues.asp?JType=IJM&VType=7&IType=7>

1. INTRODUCTION

Digitization is the word that became apple of global village's eye. Technologies are changing rapidly and emergence of new technologies. Organizations are gearing up by reevaluating their conventional outreach procedures. They are striving to the fullest to grab opportunities coming and efforts are being made to embrace the social media marketing (SMM). Social media advertising aids in marketing that in turn influences purchasers to become customer for an organization by using their products/services. SMM advertising aids effective use of social groups/community, blog advertisement, etc,

Social media Marketing (SMM) offers following preferences:

- Preference for advertisers for not only presenting items to clients but also listening to clients' grievances and suggestions.
- Simple for advertisers to differentiate associate gatherings or influencers among various groups who can be brand evangelist at about zero expense (contrasted to traditional client outreach programs) simultaneously helping for free long range Interpersonal communications. This makes effective client steadfastness.

Dilemma exists, whether the Smartphones reputation is driving the mobile application business sector, or the other way around. It is evident that mobile application stores are growing in number. Applications are built on programming languages that made latter important. The mobile application store is firmly connected with the mobile phone utilization around the world. Mobile applications keep running on mobile phones, which are effective handheld specialized gadgets with complex framework. To make use of the versatile application store market, one must grasp the elements of the mobile phone market. The mobile phone market and the mobile application business sector is increasing in civility with mobile phone shipments assessed to twofold in 2016 and with roughly 100 000 new versatile applications being transferred consistently to App store and Google Play consolidated that the mobile application business sector is developing. Advanced publicizing is becoming more brilliant, significant and less user bases are required to be ready to benefit from versatile publicizing.

Games are one among other apps in top layer from income perspective. Another conclusion drawn is numerous clients avoiding informal organizations (like Facebook and Twitter) preferring interpersonal organizations where clients just associate with few other clients. India being one of the place that displays interest in rebates, cashback and coupon locales are attempting to pick up a dependable balance in the nation, and the pattern of partner promoting is gradually gaining prominence. The usual way of doing things for these models might be distinctive, yet the centre quality continues – which is to help the shopper spare extreme cash and furnish them with an extraordinary shopping background. Also, additional work to produce deals and draw activity for the numerous online retail accomplishes they tie up. The new payment framework expected to consolidate the qualities of the more established frameworks while decreasing expenses inspection. Payments made at the POS (purpose of offer) are electronically settled and not physically performed and they don't include huge accounting or check costs in any local registry. The main trademark is closely resembling credit and platinum card exchanges, though the second trademark is comparable to coin exchange. Electronic money dispenses with real expenses connected with cash exchanges at the POS, however it lessens check and accounting costs which portray traditional card-based exchanges. From this cost sparing, it could create the impression that e-money would rule all different method for payments. In any case, electronic money bears certain holding costs (inadvertent misfortune, predestined premium, and card disappointment). These settled and holding costs give a conceivable clarification why electronic money card may not re-place other payment instruments in any event not totally. We are completely mindful of the way that most e-money frameworks that have been gone for include some local recording, so the above depiction of the e-money card innovation was admired. Right now, accessible Mondex framework looks like particularly our above portrayal as in two people can execute with each other by utilizing exclusive card peruses that are not connected to any focal recording framework. In all economies, few methods for payment coincide in parallel to each other. However, ordinarily every payment instrument overwhelms a specific exchange size or sort. This is known as the exchange space of a payment instrument.

The apparatus and methodologies for speaking with clients have changed incredibly with the development of social media marketing; organizations must figure out how to utilize social media marketing so that it is steady with their business plan. Thus, social media marketing gives another phase to brand advertising and purchasers are effectively adding to the correspondence by showcasing brands, organizations have ended up imaginative when attempting to pick up control of their marketing. Social media locales helpful for retailers to make an ordeal and retailers can utilize data on social media marketing destinations to enhance customer involvement with their image confirmed. Shoppers are no more detached beneficiaries of promoting messages; rather, they are utilizing Facebook, YouTube and Twitter to voice their assessments.

Buyers' cooperation with a brand on social media marketing fortifies the requirement for retailers to be dynamic members in personal communication and the virtual brand they create. Since social media marketing destinations can be abused for the data, it gives on purchaser conduct respects their acquiring aims, examine further that organizations ought to have long range informal communication locales into their plan of action or limited time blend.

Inorganic development procedures like mergers, acquisitions, takeovers and spinoffs are viewed as essential motors that help organizations to enter new markets, extend client base, cut rivalry, solidify and develop in size rapidly, utilize innovation as for items, individuals and procedures. Inorganic techniques are viewed by organizations as quick track procedures for development and opening of quality to shareholders. Natural methodologies allude to inward development procedures that emphasis on development by the procedure of benefit replication, abuse of innovation, better client relationship, advancement of innovation and items to fill holes in the commercial centre. Development systems allude to outside development by takeovers, mergers and acquisitions. It is quick and permits prompt usage of gained resources. It is less unsafe as it doesn't bring about extension in limit.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

- Latha Chari (2008), explained that ever since the 1990's, Indian industries have been gradually exposed to both domestic and international competition. This has led the Indian corporate segment to reorganise, to be inexpensive and deliver value to shareholders. Indian organisations have adopted organic and inorganic strategies to enrich value for their stakeholders. In advanced countries like the United States, it has been shown that inorganic value enhancing strategies like mergers, acquisitions have higher failure rates. The intention of this study is to determine whether mergers and acquisitions are noble value enhancing strategies for acquirers or for the target company, in India.
- Peter Marburger, Marzel Stratmann and Notis Pagiavlas discussed with respect to the US airline segment's mobile business. They analysed that with an efficient business model, a competitive advantage can be achieved. Significant success aspects for creating value to airline customers through mobile commercial are user involvement, the value impact of mobile technology, and customer wants. Key elements found for matching these features are accelerated facilitating processes i.e. process developments, the capability to assimilate systems into a mobile infrastructure and the devices consumers already use.
- Joerg Koenigstorfer and Andrea Klein analyzed that technological innovations are often developed to help consumers save time. However, some consumers refuse to use inventions and demote their usability with swelling usage time. The need was to find out how consumers character affects consumer behavioural choices of the mobile internet as an e.g. of new technology and how usage time affects apparent ease of use of innovative media. It shows that innovativeness, low longing for social contact and technology sanguinity in interaction with demographics regulate whether consumers choose, mobile internet services over alternatives. The results help clarify over-positive forecasts that were made in the field of technology reception.
- James E Bell explained that mobile consumers are a relatively ignored market segment. This gives a broad report on geographically mobile consumers, concentrates on the socioeconomic, lifecycle features of the mobile market, reconstructing broken shopping patterns and the capacity of the mobile division to support special marketing agendas.
- In center clarified Organic Growth and inorganic development in point of interest. Natural development is the level of a business development through an organization's own business movement, while Inorganic Growth implies that the organization has developed by merger, acquisitions or takeovers. At the point when an organization with help of its effective administration improves its development rate it is alluded to as natural development which is otherwise called Internal Growth though inorganic development is accomplished when an organization gains an innovation creating organization to upgrade its upper hand and development rate and is otherwise called External Growth.
- COLLEGIATE DECA explained that the Evolving Technology-Marketing Strategies Event involves one or two contestants designing a marketing strategy for a product or service using developing technology answers. The contestant(s) will then prove and explain the marketing plan to the impending client. The need for the year 2015-2016 is to form an inclusive emerging technology-marketing strategy for a cruise ship company

sailing to ports of call in the Caribbean, Alaska, Hawaii, and Europe. Developing technology strategies include, but are not restricted to, websites, mobile applications, social media outlets, animation, videos, and the like. The strategy should include a clearly combined brand identity for the cruise line.

- EDWARD J. GREEN discussed electronic money and emerging payments are sometimes viewed nowadays as being completely new sorts of cash. A few market analysts model them as new sorts of deal, it might be said that I'll attempt to be more particular about in a minute. Really, they are neither of these. What they are is netting plans. From this point of view, the way that developing instalment courses of action utilize new electronic advancements is truly auxiliary. It is not electronic innovation, yet rather the more profound rationale of how instalments are made, that brings up extremely troublesome issues about, for case, what is the exchange off between the economies of net instalment and the danger that multilateral mesh is thought by numerous individuals to make. (That is, there is a danger, when you are a piece of a vast instalment coalition, that somebody will neglect to whom you are not straightforwardly uncovered, but rather that the legitimate courses of action for mutualizing the misfortunes will nevertheless force a misfortune on you.) The way that new instalment game plans tend to involve production of obligation during the time spent instalment, which likewise needs to do with the rationale of how the instalments are made as opposed to with the unplanned reality that an electronic innovation is utilized, raises another arrangement of troublesome issues. We are just now starting to have sufficient speculations that address any of these issues. By a model being sufficient, here I mean basically that business analysts feel good about saying that our recommendations mirror our expert mastery, as opposed to being close to home conclusion off the highest point of our heads about what is correct or off-base. We are just toward the start of having research that we as financial experts can truly be agreeable in guaranteeing to be develop enough, all around ok ready to go up against with actualities (either as history, or econometrics proof, or whatever), to be viewed as a profoundly verified model with convincing welfare suggestions. What's more, until such research has been refined, those of us who are requested proficient guidance by policymakers are in a clumsy position. The principle indicates that I need make in these comments concern the direness of this circumstance, the high estimation of the kind of foundationally situated exploration on payments that is being displayed in this gathering, and the deception of suspecting that speedier advancement may be made if less circumspect consideration were to be paid to establishments.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT, SCOPE, OBJECTIVES AND HYPOTHESIS

1. PROBLEM STATEMENT

There is a large online market for applications created called Google play store, Apple App store which basically perform the function of digital distribution platforms for applications released by companies. The objective of this study is to understand the latest techniques employed to market Android applications and its impact and to understand Application marketing while launching new product applications and marketing of existing applications for continual survival.

2. SCOPE

The study revolves around customer preference and its related factors. The study can be extended to Mobile application marketing in general for Mobile applications on Android platform.

3. OBJECTIVES

- To study the latest organic and inorganic Android application marketing techniques and its impact.
- To understand major factors that influence customers' preference in downloading and using Android applications.
- Identify areas of development in existing techniques being used.

4. HYPOTHESES

- H₀: There is intellectual properties mutual exchange and during integration of two app development companies it would have more customers are independent of each other
H₁: There is no intellectual properties mutual exchange and during integration of two app development companies it would have more customers are dependent on each other
- H₀: There is no intellectual properties mutual exchange and during integration of two app development companies it would be Cost effective are independent of each other
H₁: There is no intellectual properties mutual exchange and during integration of two app development companies it would be Cost effective are dependent on each other
- H₀: During integration of two app development companies, they would have registered app users and the databases and during acquisition/mergers joining another app are independent of each other
H₁: During integration of two app development companies, they would have registered app users and the databases and during acquisition/mergers joining another app are dependent on each other
- H₀: During integration of two app development companies, they would have enough Finances and during acquisition/mergers, better efficiencies and better app are independent of each other
H₁: During integration of two app development companies, they would have enough Finances and during acquisition/mergers, better efficiencies and better app are dependent on each other
- H₀: During integration of two app development companies, Finances and during acquisition/mergers, more customers are independent of each other
H₁: During integration of two app development companies, Finances and during acquisition/mergers, more customers are dependent on each other
- H₀: Integration of two app development companies, have their existing strategies and cost effective are independent of each other.
H₁: Integration of two app development companies, have their existing strategies and during integration would be cost effective are dependent on each other.

4. METHODOLOGY

1. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is both exploratory and descriptive in nature and depends on both primary and secondary information. Secondary data information was gathered from the accessible sources like diaries, articles, journals and site. A sample test of 82 individuals' is chosen for the present study. The respondents were from various age bunches, gender and educational qualifications.

A close ended questionnaire was arranged and administered to discover their inclinations or preferences. As Descriptive research design are utilized when the specialist has generous information about the problem and of the variables that are to be measured. For this situation, investigated altogether and findings are

- Details of the population

The study was conducted on individuals who use mobile applications and cash back sites.

- Sample size

The total sample taken was 100, out of which 18 were incomplete, 82 were completed, and hence the number of respondents considered in the study were overall 82 in number.

- Sampling method

Convenience sampling method: Convenience sampling is a very generic term that covers wide variety of Adhoc techniques for selecting respondents. Convenience Sampling implies that the testing units are

Accessible, Convenient, simple to gauge and understandable. Considering the accessibility factor, Bengaluru zone was chosen for the study.

2. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The respondents may be careless in responding to the questionnaire.
- People are at times hesitant to respond to surveys.
- Authenticity of the response of the customer cannot be ascertained.
- The study is limited to the area Bangalore only.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Descriptive statistics is used to break down this information. The mean reactions, standard deviation and other applicable insights were figured to better comprehend the information.

The information gathered was assembled and altered to check for legitimate irregularities. The information was then coded by responses. Relationships between responses were evaluated using tables and analysis was done utilizing SPSS.

Table 1 Relationship between various variables

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.902	0.914	64

If an application development company integrates with another company of the same genre, it would have? (5 being strongly agree, 1 being strongly disagree)

Table 2 If an application development company integrates with another company of the same genre, it would have, 'Better efficiencies and better app'.

		Better Efficiencies and Better Apps			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	strongly disagree	1	1.2	1.2	1.2
	disagree	1	1.2	1.2	2.5
	neutral	14	17.3	17.3	19.8
	agree	27	33.3	33.3	53.1
	strongly agree	38	46.9	46.9	100.0
Total		81	100.0	100.0	

Inference: Out of the analyzed respondents, about 40.7 % felt that the company would have better efficiencies and better app if an application development company integrates with another company of the same genre and agreed strongly to it, 33.3% agreed, 17.3% could not draw a conclusion as they remained neutral, the remaining 1.2% strongly disagreed and disagreed to the same.

Table 3 If an application development company integrates with another company of the same genre, ‘You might consider joining another app’.

You might consider joining another app					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	strongly disagree	4	4.9	4.9	4.9
	disagree	6	7.4	7.4	12.3
	neutral	36	44.4	44.4	56.8
	agree	18	22.2	22.2	79.0
	strongly agree	17	21.0	21.0	100.0
	Total	81	100.0	100.0	

Inference: Out of the analyzed respondents, about 44.4% could not draw a conclusion as they remained neutral about the fact that they would have considered joining another app if an application development company integrates with another company of the same genre, 21% agreed strongly to it, 22.2% agreed, the remaining 4.9% and 7.4% strongly disagreed and disagreed to the same.

Table 4 If an application development company integrates with another company of the same genre, it would have, ‘more customers’.

More Customers					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	disagree	2	2.5	2.5	2.5
	neutral	25	30.9	30.9	33.3
	agree	31	38.3	38.3	71.6
	strongly agree	23	28.4	28.4	100.0
	Total	81	100.0	100.0	

Inference: Out of the analyzed respondents, about 38.3 % felt that the company would have more customers if an application development company integrates with another company of the same genre and agreed to it, 28.4% strongly agreed, 30.9% could not draw a conclusion as they remained neutral, the remaining 2.5% disagreed to the same.

During the acquisitions or mergers of application development companies, what do you think is the most important, rank them accordingly (5 being the most important and 1 being least important)

Table 5 During the acquisitions or mergers of application development companies, the most important is ‘Mutual exchange of intellectual properties’.

		Mutual exchange of intellectual properties			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all important	2	2.5	2.5	2.5
	neutral	16	19.8	19.8	22.2
	Very important	23	28.4	28.4	50.6
	Extremely important	40	49.4	49.4	100.0
	Total	81	100.0	100.0	

Inference: Out of the analyzed respondents, about 49.4 % felt that during the acquisitions or mergers of application development companies felt that ‘Mutual exchange of intellectual properties’ is an extremely important for a company, 28.4% found it very important, 19.8% could not draw a conclusion as they remained neutral, the remaining 2.5% found it not all that important.

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

Table 5 Chi square test relations between various variables.

Hypothesis	Significance level		Sig observed value	Accepted/Rejected
There is intellectual properties mutual exchange and during integration of two app development companies it would have more customers are independent of each other.	0.05%		0.015	H ₀ is rejected
There is no intellectual properties mutual exchange and during integration of two app development companies it would be Cost effective are independent of each other.	0.05%		0.071	H ₀ is accepted
During integration of two app development companies, they would have registered app users and the databases and during acquisition/mergers joining another app are independent of each other	0.05%		0.006	H ₀ is rejected

Hypothesis	Significance level		Sig observed value	Accepted/Rejected
During integration of two app development companies, they would have enough Finances and during acquisition/mergers, better efficiencies and better app are independent of each other	0.05%		0.020	H ₀ is accepted
During integration of two app development companies, Finances and during acquisition/mergers, more customers are independent of each other	0.05%		0.019	H ₀ is rejected
Integration of two app development companies, have their existing strategies and cost effective are independent of each other.	0.05%		0.027	H ₀ is rejected

6. FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. CHART FINDINGS

- With respect to devices used to access internet, it is observed that 49.9% of respondents use smart phones, 23.5% used tablet to access internet, 18.5% used laptops as means to surf the internet, 1.2% was personal computers and the rest were other type of devices.
- Out of the analyzed respondents, 30.9% of them used cash on delivery as the means for payments while purchasing, while the maximum respondents (constituted 37%) used debit cards as mean to pay for online transactions, 21% used net banking for their monthly transactions online, followed by 6.2% and 4.9% used credit cards and online checks as means of their monthly transactions online.
- Out of the analyzed respondents, about 40.7 % felt that they would do nothing if an app being used by you is bought by another app development company and agreed strongly to it, 28.4% agreed, 25.9% could not draw a conclusion as they remained neutral, the remaining 1.2% and 3.7% strongly disagreed and disagreed to the same.
- Out of the analyzed respondents, about 14.8 % felt that they would be critical of the changes if an app being used by you is bought by another app development company and agreed strongly to it, 38.3% agreed, 37% could not draw a conclusion as they remained neutral, the remaining 4.9% strongly disagreed and disagreed to the same.
- Out of the analyzed respondents, about 58.7% felt that the company would have more customers if an application development company integrates with another company of the same genre and agreed to it
- Out of the analyzed respondents, about 49.4 % felt that it would be cost effective if an application development company integrates with another company of the same genre.
- Out of the analyzed respondents, about 49.4 % felt that during the acquisitions or mergers of application development companies felt that ‘Mutual exchange of intellectual properties’ is an extremely important for a company.

- Out of the analyzed respondents, about 28.4 % felt that during the acquisitions or mergers of application development companies felt that ‘registered app users and the databases’ is extremely important for a company.
- Out of the analyzed respondents, about 28.4 % felt that during the acquisitions or mergers of application development companies felt that ‘finances’ is extremely important for a company

2. OVERALL FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

- When asked about what they would if an app being used by you is bought by another app development company, ‘do nothing’, ‘Be critical of the changes’, so if the company’s app is bought over by another company or if it merges then, it may or not lead to loss of app users.
- Smart phones are the devices used to access internet the most, it is observed that 49.9% of respondents use it to access internet, hence the company should concentrate on mobile phone users to increase their customer base and make the app more mobile operating systems compatible applications.
- With respect to devices owned, it is observed that 60.2 percent of respondents use android phones, respondents owning windows phone are in 14.8%, iPhone users constitute to about 12.3 percent and Xiomi phone users constitute up to 8.6%, the android users/play store users, the app fixes should be concentrated more on this platform as the potential users are more.
- About 58.7% felt that the company would have ‘more customers’ if an application development company integrates with another company of the same genre followed, for companies being ‘cost effective’, and about 39.5% could not draw a conclusion as they remained neutral about the fact that there would be ‘no change’, so if Pennyful as a company ever decides to integrate another company, then it may have more customers and it would be cost effective.
- When asked about what if an application development company decides to integrate with another company of the same genre, majority of them felt that both the companies would have ‘better efficiencies and better app’, hence if ever Pennyful acquires or merges with another company, it might have better efficiencies and better app.
- During the acquisitions or mergers of application development companies, ‘finances’, ‘existing strategies’, ‘mutual exchange of intellectual properties’, ‘registered app users and the databases’, and ‘existing infrastructure’, these were important for both the companies, hence if ever Pennyful acquires or merges with another company, it should concentrate more on these.

7. CONCLUSION

A company like pennyful should work more on customization and design of the apps, constantly undertake study of its profits and the cause for it. Regularly take up customer’s reviews and should make necessary efforts on improving apps. Be creative in advertising and grabbing customer attention and make a sustainable development.

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